

Plant-based

Fermentation

Cultivated

Germany's alternative protein research ecosystem

Alternative proteins – plant-based, fermentation-derived or cultivated – offer a promising solution to meet the projected growth in the global demand for meat, seafood, eggs, and dairy, while building a more sustainable food system.

Leading research organisations

Unique publications

510 publications

#1 in publication volume in Europe
+256% from 2020 to 2025

828 patents

#4 in published patent volume in Europe

Total public funding

Million € · 2020-2025

Funding per capita

€ per person · 2020-2025

If Germany makes alternative proteins a strategic priority, the sector could contribute significantly to the country's economy by 2045

€65B

annual economic contribution

+250,000

jobs supported